

CO-DESIGNING NEIGHBOURHOOD REGENERATION

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GINNGER enhances regeneration actions ensuring residents' voices are heard throughout the process.

To achieve this, we combine a **co-creation methodology** with **13 digital solutions** and test our approach in six European cities to encourage energy efficiency, green mobility and sustainable use of resources.

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